

Table S1. Imprecision and accuracy in nail and hair samples at low (30 pg/mg), medium (75 pg/mg or 750 pg/mg) and high (750 pg/mg or 7500 pg/mg) QC concentrations.

	Analyte	Intra-assay imprecision (n=15; %CV)			Inter-assay imprecision (n=15; %CV)			Total imprecision (n=15; %CV)			Accuracy (n=15; %)		
		LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Nail samples	Venlafaxine	5.2	3.1	2.3	1.0	5.4	6.7	5.3	6.2	7.1	100.6	103.3	99.2
	Trazodone	4.2	3.8	3.0	3.3	5.2	4.3	5.3	6.4	5.3	104.6	99.0	104.8
	Citalopram	5.2	2.4	3.0	2.9	4.1	5.5	6.0	4.8	6.2	103.4	100.3	99.1
	Paroxetine	4.4	3.0	3.0	3.1	2.2	1.2	5.4	3.7	3.2	104.8	104.4	103.1
	Fluoxetine	4.0	3.7	2.9	2.2	0.0	2.0	4.5	3.7	3.5	107.58	103.4	94.7
	Sertraline	5.0	3.5	3.0	2.3	3.1	4.9	5.5	4.6	5.7	106.26	102.8	97.5
	Zolpidem	6.1	4.8	5.5	0.0	4.6	5.2	6.1	6.7	7.6	102.2	100.9	101.5
	Oxazepam	9.4	3.9	6.2	1.9	5.9	6.9	9.6	7.0	9.3	102.9	101.1	98.8
	Alprazolam	5.8	6.2	7.6	2.6	4.1	4.4	6.4	7.4	8.7	99.9	103.3	93.8
	Lorazepam	4.0	4.7	3.4	5.4	1.8	4.1	6.7	5.0	5.3	100.8	105.6	99.6
	Nordiazepam	5.1	3.8	2.3	2.8	0.0	4.5	5.8	3.8	5.1	105.5	101.7	97.8
	Diazepam	4.8	9.4	7.0	5.9	5.7	0.0	7.6	11.0	7.0	99.8	100.9	93.8
Hair samples	Venlafaxine	7.3	3.3	4.1	0.0	0.7	1.3	7.3	3.4	4.2	102.3	100.9	101.1
	Trazodone	7.1	2.0	2.3	0.0	1.4	3.1	7.1	2.4	3.8	103.6	105.0	97.6
	Citalopram	6.8	4.6	5.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.8	4.6	5.6	98.0	96.9	99.0
	Paroxetine	7.1	3.8	3.4	0.0	2.0	1.3	7.1	4.3	3.7	99.7	101.8	106.5
	Fluoxetine	5.0	4.3	2.9	2.9	0.0	2.1	5.8	4.3	3.6	102.2	102.9	100.5
	Sertraline	7.6	4.2	4.1	0.0	0.0	0.4	7.6	4.2	4.1	101.5	100.9	101.3
	Zolpidem	4.6	3.8	3.6	0.0	2.2	2.1	4.6	4.4	4.1	100.3	100.3	99.0
	Oxazepam	6.1	4.1	3.9	2.3	1.0	0.0	6.5	4.2	3.9	99.1	105.6	102.7
	Alprazolam	4.7	4.3	3.8	2.5	0.8	0.3	5.3	4.3	3.8	104.8	99.4	99.1
	Lorazepam	5.0	5.0	4.8	4.7	2.3	0.0	6.9	5.5	4.8	100.7	100.2	99.1
	Nordiazepam	4.6	3.7	6.2	2.2	2.0	0.0	5.1	4.2	6.2	103.7	103.6	96.6
	Diazepam	7.2	4.5	5.3	2.0	2.8	0.0	7.5	5.3	5.3	99.0	102.8	99.5

Table S2. Autosampler stability (%loss) in nail and hair samples at low (30 pg/mg), medium (75 pg/mg or 750 pg/mg) and high (750 pg/mg or 7500 pg/mg) QC concentrations.

Analyte	Concentration	%Loss	
		Nail samples (24h)	Hair samples (72h)
Venlafaxine	LOW	1.5	-3.0
	MEDIUM	0.4	-2.1
	HIGH	0.9	2.3
Trazodone	LOW	-1.3	-7.3
	MEDIUM	-2.3	-5.0
	HIGH	1.1	-0.2
Citalopram	LOW	-0.6	-3.2
	MEDIUM	-0.4	-1.8
	HIGH	0.6	0.8
Paroxetine	LOW	1.3	5.4
	MEDIUM	0.5	0.4
	HIGH	1.6	1.4
Fluoxetine	LOW	0.6	1.8
	MEDIUM	0.7	-0.7
	HIGH	1.3	-3.6
Sertraline	LOW	-1.8	-0.3
	MEDIUM	-2.6	3.7
	HIGH	-1.8	1.6
Zolpidem	LOW	2.9	-4.1
	MEDIUM	0.8	-5.2
	HIGH	-2.4	-3.8
Oxazepam	LOW	0.6	1.9
	MEDIUM	2.5	-6.8
	HIGH	-1.8	3.7
Alprazolam	LOW	0.4	-4.8
	MEDIUM	5.4	-5.1
	HIGH	-0.2	6.1
Lorazepam	LOW	-3.4	-6.5
	MEDIUM	5.0	6.7
	HIGH	-0.5	-0.6
Nordiazepam	LOW	-4.3	-2.7
	MEDIUM	-6.9	-6.8
	HIGH	-3.7	-1.8
Diazepam	LOW	-3.1	6.3
	MEDIUM	-0.3	7.5
	HIGH	1.8	1.8